

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Melibiose and Cellobiose by Alkaline Aqueous Iodine Solution

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A kinetic study has been made of oxidation of melibiose and cellobiose by alkaline aqueous iodine at different pH. The results indicate that the active oxidising species is hypoiodous acid. The maximum oxidation in each case is found around pH 11.4. A first order dependence in hypoiodous acid, in melibiose and in cellobiose has been observed. Change in ionic strength of the medium shows no effect on the reaction rate. A probable mechanism consistent with the experimental results has been proposed.

KINETIC investigations of the oxidation of reducing sugars and iodine in alkaline solution have been reported by many workers¹⁻³. The present study aims at getting more information about the oxidation of melibiose and cellobiose by iodine in alkaline medium with a view to characterizing the active oxidising species of iodine in aqueous solution of alkaline buffer and proposing a suitable mechanism.

Experimental

Reagents used were of A. R. grade (B. D. H. and E. Merck) samples. Aqueous solutions of melibiose and cellobiose (L. C. grade) were freshly prepared. Solution of iodine (in 0.1 M KI) was prepared. To the requisite volumes of buffer solutions of desired pH and the substrates maintained at the desired temperatures was added required volumes of iodine solution which too was maintained at the temperature of the reaction. The kinetics of the reaction were followed by removing aliquots (5 ml) from the reaction mixture at different intervals of time and the reaction was stopped by adding cold 3% sulphuric acid (50 ml). The iodine liberated was immediately titrated against 2.00×10^{-2} M sodium thiosulphate solution. Reproducible results were always obtained.

Results and Discussion

The oxidation of melibiose and cellobiose by iodine was investigated at several initial concentrations of the oxidant. It was observed that the rate of oxidation was independent of the variation of concentration of iodine. The values of k_s (standard zero order rate constant) for many-fold variation of iodine in case of melibiose and cellobiose were found to be 4.96, 5.10, 4.96, 5.10, 4.90×10^{-5} and 2.80, 2.40, 2.80, 2.50, 2.50×10^{-5} mol dm³ min⁻¹ respectively. The constant values of k_s obtained for variation of iodine concentration in

case of melibiose and cellobiose clearly indicate zero order kinetics with respect to iodine.

In order to determine the order of the reaction with respect to reducing substrates, the reactions were studied at different concentrations of the substrates. A perusal of Table 1 shows that reactions have first order dependence on melibiose and cellobiose.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF CONCENTRATION OF SUBSTRATES

Melibiose : Temp. = 30°, pH = 9.8, [I ₂] = 7.10 × 10 ⁻⁵ M		Cellobiose : Temp. = 30°, pH = 10.3, [I ₂] = 8.42 × 10 ⁻⁵ M			
[Melibiose] × 10 ⁻³ M	k _s × 10 ⁻⁵ cm ⁻³ min ⁻¹	k _s × 10 ⁻⁵ min ⁻¹	[Cellobiose] × 10 ⁻³ M	k _s × 10 ⁻⁵ cm ⁻³ min ⁻¹	k _s × 10 ⁻⁵ min ⁻¹
3.00	2.20	7.33	8.00	1.80	6.00
4.00	2.90	7.25	4.00	2.40	6.00
5.00	3.60	7.20	5.00	3.10	6.20
6.00	4.40	7.33	6.00	3.60	6.00
7.00	5.70	7.12	7.00	4.20	6.00
10.0	7.20	7.20	8.00	4.80	6.00
12.0	8.00	7.33	9.00	5.40	6.00

The results of the effect of pH on the rate of oxidation show that reaction rate was maximum in the vicinity of pH 11.4 and decreases on either sides of this range (Table 2). The values of k_s (Table 2) vary with the change in concentration of

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF pH ON REACTION RATE

Temp. = 30°, [Melibiose] = 10.00 × 10 ⁻³ M, [I ₂] = 7.10 × 10 ⁻⁵ M		[Cellobiose] = 10.00 × 10 ⁻³ M, [I ₂] = 8.42 × 10 ⁻⁵ M			
pH	k _s × 10 ⁻⁵ M cm ⁻³ min ⁻¹	[HOI] × 10 ⁻⁴ M	pH	k _s × 10 ⁻⁵ M cm ⁻³ min ⁻¹	[HOI] × 10 ⁻⁴ M
9.80	3.60	0.42	9.80	4.50	0.50
10.5	4.90	2.06	10.10	5.00	0.99
10.7	5.20	3.19	10.80	5.50	4.65
10.9	7.10	4.78	11.00	8.40	7.00
11.1	10.0	6.73	11.2	10.6	9.18
11.5	14.0	9.35	11.4	13.0	11.0
11.8	8.00	7.88	11.7	11.60	10.4
12.2	5.00	4.06	11.9	8.40	8.20
			12.2	6.60	5.00

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hypoiodous acid or pH. Hence order of the reaction with respect to hypoiodous acid is unity. The plot of the rate of oxidation vs pH was found to be identical with the plot of [HOI] vs pH.

The reactions were found to be affected by the increase in temperature. The values of activation parameters are shown in Table 3.

TABLE 3—VALUES OF ACTIVATION PARAMETERS

Substrate	E_a kcal mol ⁻¹	$\Delta H^\ddagger$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$\Delta S^\ddagger$ e.u.	$\Delta E^\ddagger$ kcal mol ⁻¹
Melibiose	12.4	11.8	-22.8	18.6
Cellobiose	11.5	10.9	-21.1	17.2

With melibiose and cellobiose, the effect of adding varying amounts of KCl to the reaction mixture was examined, but no appreciable salt-effect was detected. The absence of salt-effect indicates that the reaction does not take place between ionic substances. Hence at least one of the reactants must be non-ionic. This confirms that the reaction takes place between substrate (melibiose and cellobiose) and hypoiodous acid.

The above findings clearly suggest single mechanism for the oxidation of melibiose and cellobiose. Further the rate-determining step is the action of hypoiodous acid on organic substrate which probably forms a complex which further gives products. The following probable rate law might be proposed,

$$-\frac{d[\text{HOI}]}{dt} = k[\text{S}][\text{HOI}]$$

where [S] represents the concentration of melibiose or cellobiose. Before coming to the actual mechanism it would be more appropriate to discuss the reacting species of iodine in alkaline buffer solution.

A detailed survey of literature reveals that iodine dissolved in alkaline medium⁴ gives hypoiodous acid along with hypoiodite and triiodide ions. The disproportionation of hypoiodite into iodate is not considered because of the fact that iodate has no action on aldose sugars. It has been necessary to calculate the concentration of the probable oxidising species, hypoiodous acid and hypoiodite ion, either of which can be responsible for oxidation. The following equilibrium constants⁵ are considered for calculating the concentrations of hypoiodous acid and hypoiodite ion.

$$K_1 = 3 \times 10^{-13} = \frac{[\text{H}^+][\text{I}^-][\text{HOI}]}{[\text{I}_2]} \quad (\text{I})$$

$$K_2 = 10^{-11} = \frac{[\text{H}^+][\text{OI}^-]}{[\text{HOI}]} \quad (\text{II})$$

$$K_3 = 1.36 \times 10^{-8} = \frac{[\text{I}_2][\text{I}^-]}{[\text{I}_3^-]} \quad (\text{III})$$

Thus taking into consideration the formation of the ions mentioned above,

$[\text{I}_2] + [\text{HOI}] + [\text{IO}^-] + [\text{I}_3^-] = \text{Total concn. of iodine.}$
From this relationship approximate values of hypoiodous acid and hypoiodite ions are calculated.

The effect of pH (9.80–12.20) on the rate of oxidation has been studied. The results (Table 2) reveal that the rate of oxidation increases first with the rise of pH in the lower pH range, reaches maximum in the vicinity of pH 11.40 where the concentration of hypoiodous acid is maximum and then decreases in the higher alkaline pH range. In the higher alkaline range the concentration of hypoiodous acid decreases probably due to its conversion into hypoiodite ion which is a slower oxidising agent than undissociated hypoiodous acid. A plot of the rate of oxidation vs pH was found identical with the plot of [HOI] vs pH. This leads to the conclusion that the active oxidising species in each case is the unionised hypoiodous acid. This is further supported by the study of the oxidation of aldoses with bromine⁶ in alkaline medium in which it has been suggested that the hypobromous acid is the predominant oxidising species in the alkaline pH. The extent of [HOI] in the mechanism is in the range $0.42-9.35 \times 10^{-4} M$ at pH range 9.80–11.40 (Table 2). The values of equilibrium activation constant for such reactions are 2.618×10^{-14} and 2.917×10^{-15} for melibiose and cellobiose respectively at 25° and pH 10.70. The stoichiometric studies show that one mole of I_2 was required to oxidise each mole of substrate.

On the basis of the results the following mechanism may be proposed in order to explain the mechanistic path of the oxidation of aldo sugars,

Now the rate of formation of complex will be given as

$$\frac{d[\text{complex}]}{dt} = k_1 [\text{S}] [\text{HOI}] - k_{-1} [\text{complex}] - k_2 [\text{complex}] \quad (\text{1})$$

At steady state conditions,

$$\frac{d[\text{complex}]}{dt} = 0 \quad (\text{2})$$

From equations (1) and (2) the concentration of complex comes out to be

$$[\text{Complex}] = \frac{k_1 [\text{S}] [\text{HOI}]}{k_{-1} + k_2} \quad (\text{3})$$

Now at steady state conditions the rate of disappearance of HOI may be given as

$$-\frac{d[\text{HOI}]}{dt} = k_2 [\text{complex}] \quad (4)$$

$$= \frac{k_1 k_2 [\text{S}][\text{HOI}]}{k_{-1} + k_2} \quad (5)$$

Now the total $[\text{HOI}]_T$ may be considered as

$$[\text{HOI}]_T = [\text{HOI}] + [\text{complex}] \quad (6)$$

Now substituting the value of $[\text{complex}]$, the equation (6) reduces to

$$[\text{HOI}]_T = [\text{HOI}] + \frac{k_1 [\text{S}][\text{HOI}]}{k_{-1} + k_2} \quad (7)$$

Rearranging the equation (7) the value of free $[\text{HOI}]$ comes out to be

$$[\text{HOI}] = \frac{(k_{-1} + k_2) [\text{HOI}]_T}{(k_{-1} + k_2) + k_1 [\text{S}]} \quad (8)$$

From equations (5) and (8) the final rate law comes out to be

$$-\frac{d[\text{HOI}]}{dt} = \frac{k_1 k_2 [\text{S}](k_{-1} + k_2) [\text{HOI}]_T}{\{k_{-1} + k_2 + k_1 [\text{S}]\}(k_{-1} + k_2)} \\ = \frac{k_1 k_2 [\text{S}][\text{HOI}]_T}{(k_{-1} + k_2) + k_1 [\text{S}]} \quad (9)$$

In the present experimental conditions one might assume the following inequality,

$$k_{-1} + k_2 > k_1 [\text{S}]$$

and hence equation (9) reduces to

$$-\frac{d[\text{HOI}]}{dt} = \frac{k_1 k_2 [\text{S}][\text{HOI}]_T}{k_{-1} + k_2} = k [\text{S}][\text{HOI}]_T \quad (10)$$

where $k = \frac{k_1 k_2}{(k_{-1} + k_2)}$

Now equation (10) clearly indicates first order kinetics with respect to substrate and hypoiodous acid concentrations. The valid rate law equation (10) is tested by the plot of $-dc/dt$ vs $[\text{HOI}]_T$ and $[\text{S}]$ separately.

The activation energy have been found to be 12.42 and 11.52 kcal mol⁻¹ for melibiose and cellobiose respectively. The low values of activation energy indicate that at least one of the reacting substances of rate determining reaction may be neutral molecule. No salt-effect is also consistent with a rate-determining reaction involving neutral molecules. Therefore, our proposed reaction mechanism

is in agreement with the results of activation energy obtained for the aforesaid aldo sugars.

The value of equivalence for the oxidation of melibiose and cellobiose by iodine in alkaline solution is approximately one in each case. Hence the overall reaction products are

(Aldonic acid)

where R is carbohydrate chain. The reaction products have been confirmed by Judd⁶, Macleod and Robinson⁷ and it has been further confirmed by paper chromatography.

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